

METHODS OF COMMITTING AND CONCEALING THE CRIME OF EXTORTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10716085>

Abstract: This article analyzes the method of committing and concealing this crime as part of the criminalistic description of the crime of extortion. In the course of the analysis, the definitions and opinions of a number of criminologists regarding this crime were presented.

Key words: extortion, crime, method, criminalistic description, concealment, motive, victim.

Criminalistic description of crimes consists of generalized evidentiary data on the most important aspects of the considered types of socially dangerous, illegal acts defined in the criminal law, and a system of scientific conclusions and recommendations based on them. Knowledge of criminalistic descriptions is necessary to organize a fast, comprehensive and impartial investigation of criminal cases. [1]

One of the successful definitions, in our opinion, was made by Professor A.N. Kolesnichenko. He called the criminalistic description "...a system of information on the criminalistically significant features of certain types of crimes, which reflects the natural connection between them and serves to build and verify investigative paths in the investigation of specific crimes." described as.

According to the research conducted by S.I. Konovalov [2], until now there are almost twenty different elements in various variants and combinations of the criminalistic description. It is clear that it is not only impossible to include all possible elements of a crime scene, but it does not bring significant benefits in the detection and investigation of a crime. From our point of view, the most important thing that effectively helps in the investigation of a particular crime is to determine the natural connection and connection between these elements.

Of course, the main practical benefit of criminalistic description is the ability to know some elements and calculate the missing and unknown ones. Therefore, when considering the criminalistic features of extortion, we tried to at least establish relationships between its individual elements.

One of the main elements of the criminalistic features of extortion is information about the subject of the criminal attack. It is known that identifying the subject of an attack during the investigation of a specific crime helps to determine a number of other important circumstances of the case, in particular, information about the identity of the criminal, the level of awareness of the victim's income. Thus, as noted by V.V. Bugai, identifying the subject of a criminal attack during extortion always helps to quickly and correctly eliminate other cases of this type of crime. [3]

In cases of this category, the person himself can be considered as a subject of criminal aggression in the criminalistic sense. In this sense, according to M. V. Saltevskiy, unlike the concept of criminal law, the subject of a direct attack can be a person. In addition, the analysis of investigative practice shows that such persons are often highly financially secure individuals in cases of extortion.

The issue of the concept and structure of the method of committing a crime has been widely considered in the literature of criminalistics. Also, T.N. Mudyugin, who was the first to analyze the content of the method of committing a crime, proposed to distinguish the concepts of "method of committing" and "method of concealing a crime". He defines the method of execution as "a set of actions committed by a criminal in a certain order and aimed at achieving a criminal goal." The method of concealment is aimed at hiding the crime from others, first of all from the investigative bodies, in order to avoid responsibility for the crime committed as an act. [4]

Taking into account the structure of the method of committing a crime, which includes an interconnected system of actions of criminals (preparation, execution and concealment), L. Ya. Drapkin and M. S. Utkin proposed to classify the methods of committing a crime according to the level of complexity in the following scope and content:

- 1) complete or most qualified methods characterized by the actions of criminals in preparing, committing and concealing crimes;
- 2) less qualified or shortened methods of the first type, in which there are no preparatory actions for committing a crime in the presence of interrelated methods;
- 3) less qualified or reduced methods of the second type, which do not contain methods of concealing crimes when there are preparatory actions in their composition;
- 4) simplified methods that do not have subsystems of actions to prepare and hide the crime. [5]

Many criminalists combine the concept of "method of committing a crime" with the activities of preparing, committing and concealing a crime, and believe that all these activities are aimed at achieving a single criminal goal. Some scientists emphasize that the sequence of actions performed by the criminal, which constitutes the method of committing a crime, can be different. The order of these actions is largely related to the characteristics of committing certain types of crimes.

The initial stage of extortion begins with the demand from criminals to "pay" for some action or inaction. Such requests can be expressed through personal contact between the criminal and the victim or indirectly: by phone or in writing.

At the stage of direct execution of criminal acts, i.e., when taking possession of the subject of extortion, as a rule, criminals determine the time, place and method of carrying it out themselves. The transfer can be made directly from the victim to the perpetrator (manually). In this case, extortionists usually choose dark times and sparse locations. Obtaining the subject of extortion can also be done through intermediaries.

When committing extortion, criminals make efforts to hide the crime, sometimes it cannot be distinguished from the efforts to commit it. In this case, the extortionist mainly pursues the following goals:

- a) hiding the fact of committing a crime;
- b) concealment of extortion by an organized criminal group;
- c) create the impression that the transfer is voluntary (in the form of payment of a debt, loan, etc.);
- d) creating a false situation (allegedly, a crime was committed by another person and he himself had to take certain valuables from the victim);
- e) hiding or destroying the tools used in committing the crime;
- f) to eliminate traces of his involvement in crime.

Among the methods used by criminals to hide extortion, the following can be noted: the demand to exchange banknotes at the time of handover, fearing that the numbers will be rewritten; unexpected change of the place of delivery of the subject of extortion (also includes cases where the victim meets the middleman at a conditional place and takes him to another place); searching for the victim during the transfer of the subject of extortion in order to identify the recording device; If witnesses and victims report extortion to the internal affairs department, they are threatened with certain negative consequences, and so on.

The conducted research allowed the author to distinguish the characteristics of the objects of criminal attacks in the commission of extortion and to determine their influence on the method of committing this crime. But it is known that the object of criminal attack and the method of committing the crime are not the only structural elements of criminalistic features of crimes. They also contain information about the circumstances of the crime and the identity of the criminal and the victim. At the same time, it is necessary to emphasize once again that our study of various elements of the criminalistic description of extortion was aimed at determining the interrelationship between them and identifying possible traces of this crime. Also, identifying and studying the problem allows for more effective detection and investigation of this type of criminal activity.

References:

1. Криминалистика. Дарслик. Ф.А.Абдумажидов, Р.А.Алимова, А.Норбоев, А.С.Закутский ва бошқалар. – Тошкент: ТДЮУ, 2003. – 11-12-б.
2. Коновалов С.И. Теоретико-методологические проблемы криминалистики. — Ростов на Дону. — 2001. — С. 82-85.
3. Бугай В.В. Расследование вымогательства в кн. Криминалистика: Расследование преступлений в сфере экономики / под ред. проф. В.Д. Грабовского, доц. А.Ф. Лубина. — Н.Новгород. — 1995. — С. 285.
4. Васильев А.Н., Мудьюгин Г.Н., Якубович Н.А. Планирование расследования преступления. - М.: Госюриздат, 1957. - С.66.
5. Драпкин Л.Я., Уткин М.С. Понятие и структура способа совершения преступления. // Проблемы борьбы с преступностью. - ВШ МВД СССР, Омск, 1978. С.133-134.

